

DETACHED-EDDY SIMULATION OF THE INTERACTION OF STATOR WAKE AND ROTOR TIP LEAKAGE FLOW IN A LAST STAGE STEAM TURBINE

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ABSTRACT

Investigation of the tip leakage flow structure in unshrouded last stage steam turbines is important for it can influence the aerodynamic loading at blade tip and the rotor flutter characteristics. The modern last stage steam turbines generally have a transonic tip speed, and thus the tip leakage flow can be sensitive to small disturbance such as the upstream stator wakes. Previous research found that the interaction between stator wakes and tip leakage flow cannot be resolved by numerical simulation based on URANS equations, for the transonic tip clearance flow has a complex structure which beyond the predictive capability of turbulence models. In this study, the influence of stator wake on the tip leakage flow structure in a last stage steam turbine is investigated by both URANS and the Detached-Eddy Simulation (DES) method. The ability of DES to resolve the transonic tip clearance flow structure has been verified in the previous study. A 3D realistic-scale last stage steam turbine model is used as the research object. Numerical results illustrate that the distortion generated by stator wakes has a minor influence on the stage performance and the tip leakage vortex structure, but it contributes to a periodic motion and migration of the induced vortices. The interaction between stator wakes and induced vortices are not fully resolved in URANS results. Therefore, a significant difference in unsteady blade loading between DES and URANS results is shown on the rear half of blade suction side near the tip. Meanwhile, the periodic motion and migration of induced vortices due to the stator wake effect decrease the difference in steady blade loading between URANS and DES results. Further investigation of the importance of multi-row effects on steam turbine flutter characteristics will be conducted in the future.

NOMENCLATURE AND ACRONYMS

$C_{DES}\Delta$	local mesh scale
D_{DES}^k	dissipative term of the k-transport equation in DES

$E(\kappa)$	energy spectrum function
$l_{k-\omega}$	local turbulent length scale in the SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model
l_{DES}	local turbulent length scale in DES model
k	turbulent kinetic energy
κ	wave number
β	SST Closure Constant
η	Kolmogorov length scale
ρ	density
ω	turbulence frequency
H_n	normalized helicity
$\vec{\xi}$	relative flow velocity
$\vec{\omega}$	absolute vorticity
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DES	Detached-Eddy Simulation
LE	Leading Edge
LES	Large-Eddy Simulation
PS	Pressure Side
SS	Suction Side
TE	Trailing edge
(U)RANS	(Unsteady) Reynolds-averaged Navier–Stokes equations

INTRODUCTION

Investigation of the tip leakage flow structure in unshrouded last stage steam turbines is of great importance, for it can have a significant influence on the blade loading at the tip region and the rotor flutter characteristics [1,2]. Studies on the tip leakage flow structure without inlet distortions had been widely analyzed by both experiments [3, 4] and numerical simulations [5]. Investigation on a low-speed compressor [5] by Large-Eddy Simulation (LES)

separated the vortices in tip clearance flow into three types: the tip leakage vortex, the tip separation vortex, and the induced vortex. The classification of vortices in the tip region of compressors agreed with the experimental results in turbines [3, 4]. However, different from the tip clearance flow in compressors, the tip leakage vortices in turbines are always close to the suction side of the blade due to the interaction between tip clearance flow and the main flow.

Modern last stage steam turbines generally have a transonic tip speed, and thus the tip leakage flow structure can be sensitive to small disturbances. One of the dominant sources of unsteady disturbances in steam turbines is the upstream stator wakes. Most of the previous work on the interaction between stator wakes and rotor tip leakage flow focused on its influence on the aerodynamic loss in compressors [6-11]. Interaction between the wake-induced pressure pulse and tip flow can enhance the rotor performance by reducing the tip flow loss, if the frequency of the stator wakes is appropriately designed [7]. Experimental results on axial compressors [8,10] illustrated that the upstream wake could introduce a periodic fluctuation in the instantaneous tip clearance vortices structure. Research on the interaction between stator wake and rotor tip leakage flow in turbines [12-14] presented a similar phenomenon in the transformation of instantaneous tip leakage flow structure. The influence of that interaction on the performance of turbines was relatively smaller than that of compressors.

However, the transformation of tip leakage flow due to wake effects observed in experiments [10] was not resolved in a corresponding numerical simulation based on URANS equations [11]. Riera [6] investigated the periodical fluctuation of tip leakage vortices due to the wake effect on a high-pressure transonic compressor by both URANS and Zonal Detached-Eddy Simulation (ZDES) approaches. The ZDES method successfully resolved the interaction between tip clearance flow and stators wakes, while the URANS method failed. The reason is that the transonic tip clearance flow has a complex structure which beyond the predictive capability of URANS [15-17]. These prior research illustrated that the high-fidelity numerical approaches are necessary for the analysis of upstream wakes influence on tip clearance flow.

As far as we are aware, URANS is the highest fidelity numerical method applied in the analysis of steam turbine stator wakes-tip leakage flow interaction yet. The Detached-Eddy Simulation (DES) method is used in this study to resolve the interaction between stator wake and tip leakage flow. The ability of DES to resolve the transonic tip clearance flow structure has been verified in Ref. 15 and 16. In this paper, the interaction between stator wake and rotor tip leakage flow is analyzed on a 3D realistic-scale last stage steam turbine model by both URANS and DES approaches.

NUMERICAL APPROACH

The commercial software ANSYS CFX is applied as the CFD solver. In CFX calculations, the high-resolution

scheme is used to calculate the advection term and turbulence numerics, and the second-order backward Euler scheme is used for time integration. In the time-transient simulations, 256 physical time-steps are included in a stator passing period, and a maximum of 50 inner steps are included in a physical time-step, which follows the numerical set-ups that have been verified in Ref. 15. The time-averaged flow field and unsteady pressure fluctuation are calculated until a periodic flow solution is achieved. Two numerical approaches were applied in the simulation of the transient flow field: URANS and DES. The SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model is applied in the URANS simulations.

Detached-Eddy Simulation

Detached-Eddy Simulation (DES) is a hybrid LES/RANS method. The concept of DES is to calculate the boundary layer by a RANS turbulence model and switching the turbulence model into a LES mode in detached regions [18]. The DES applied in this study is based on SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model [19]. Two transport equations are solved in SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model, including one for the kinetic energy k and one for the turbulence frequency ω . Comparing with the standard SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model, a limiter is added in the formulation of the eddy-viscosity and thus modify the production term of ω in SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model.

In DES calculation, the LES is switched from URANS when the turbulence length predicted by the URANS is larger than the local grid spacing. The turbulence length scale in SST $k-\omega$ turbulence model and DES can be presented as Eq. 1 and 2, respectively.

$$l_{k-\omega} = k^{0.5} / (\beta * \omega) \quad (1)$$

$$l_{DES} = \min(l_{k-\omega}, C_{DES}\Delta) \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the dissipative term of the k -transport Equation in DES is transferred to Eq. 3.

$$D_{DES}^k = \rho k^{2/3} / l_{DES} \quad (3)$$

STEAM TURBINE TEST CASE

A 3D realistic-scale last stage steam turbine is applied as the research object. The geometry of this turbine is first designed by Durham University [20]. The original model has a 60 blades stator stage and a 65 blades rotor stage. In this study, the amount of stator blade is modified as 65 to reduce the number of blade passages while assuring a 1:1 stator/rotor interface. The rotor blade has a 67 degrees stagger angle at the tip and an average length of 920 mm. The tip gap distance is set at 4.2 mm, which is 0.45% of the blade height. Schematic figure of this steam turbine model is presented in Fig. 1.

Fig.1 Schematic figure of the steam turbine test case

Computation domain

The computation domain includes one blade-to-blade passage of the stator and one blade-to-blade passage of the rotor. The periodic boundary condition is applied on the blade-to-blade interfaces. Positions of the inlet, outlet and stator/rotor interface boundaries are shown in Fig. 1. The inlet boundary condition is generated by Alstom Power from a previous multi-stage calculation, which includes a circumferential-averaged profile of total pressure, total temperature and the direction of velocity^[20]. Considering that an averaged static pressure outlet boundary condition can lead to different outlet profiles in different cases, a constant value of static pressure equals 8800 Pa is set on the outlet boundary.

Mesh description

The mesh of stator domain is made by TurboGrid, which has 0.7 million nodes and an average y^+ equals 1.2 on the boundaries. The mesh of rotor domain is generated by ICEM and refined near the tip for DES analyses. It has 9.42 million nodes in total, in which 4.30 million nodes are located in the top 10% span. The averaged y^+ on the boundaries of rotor domain is smaller than 1. In the tip clearance region, an O-block is applied and thus the nodes had a 1:1 connection in the tip gap. The maximum cell length scale in the three directions is smaller than 1.0 mm in the tip clearance flow region. Snapshots of the grid in the rotor domain at the shroud and the mid-chord plane are presented in Fig. 2. Verification of the mesh independence in DES analysis is presented in Ref. 15.

(a)

(b)

Figure 2. Snapshots of the mesh in rotor domain at (a) shroud and (b) mid-chord plane

Numerical cases

In this study, the initial result of the flow field is calculated by RANS analysis, in which the stator/rotor interface uses a stage averaged velocity boundary condition. Based on the initial result, two different sets of unsteady simulations are calculated to investigate the influence of stator wakes on tip clearance flow. Simulations in the first set use the stage averaged velocity boundary condition on the stator/rotor interface to remove the impact of unsteady stator wakes. Simulations in the second set apply the transient rotor-stator boundary condition at the stator/rotor interface, which can transfer the unsteady distortion generated by stator wakes to the rotor domain. In each set of the simulations, both URANS and DES method are applied.

The four simulation cases are named URANS-Ave, DES-Ave, URANS-Wake, and DES-Wake. The “-Ave” represents the averaged stator/rotor interface applied in the first set of simulations, while the “-Wake” represents the second set of simulations that resolving the influence of unsteady stator wakes on rotor tip clearance flow.

RESULTS

Total Performance

The time-averaged mass flow rate and the total to static isentropic efficiency of the turbine stage are presented in Tab.1. The interaction between unsteady stator wake and rotor blade slightly decreases the stage efficiency. The influence of numerical approaches and unsteady stators wakes on overall stage performance is minor.

Table 1. Total performance for difference cases

Case	Mass flow [kg/s]	Efficiency [%]
URANS-Ave	83.61	87.41
DES-Ave	83.61	87.42
URANS-Wake	83.63	87.20
DES-Wake	83.64	87.13

Turbulence characteristics

The energy spectrum of velocity calculated in the tip clearance flow region (a straight line in the core of the tip leakage vortex) of DES-Ave and DES-Wake results is shown in Fig. 3. The distribution of turbulence kinetic energy follows the inertial subrange slopes. The energy level is higher at every turbulence length scale in DES-Wake case, which indicates that the interaction with stator wakes significantly increase the turbulence intensity in the tip clearance flow region.

Figure 3. Energy spectrum function $E(\kappa)$ versus Kolmogorov length scale η multiply wave number κ in the tip region

Tip clearance flow structure

The resolved tip clearance flow structures from the four cases are presented in Fig. 4. The vortex core region is captured by Q criterion [21] and colored by normalized helicity. The normalized helicity H_n is calculated by

$$H_n = \frac{\vec{\omega} \cdot \vec{\xi}}{|\vec{\omega}| |\vec{\xi}|} \quad (4)$$

where $\vec{\omega}$ and $\vec{\xi}$ denote vectors of the absolute vorticity and the relative flow velocity, respectively. The magnitude of H_n represents the normalized vortex strength, and the symbol of H_n represents the direction of vortices. The tip leakage vortex is marked by blue colour in the contour (where the helicity is negative), and the contrarotative induced vortices are marked by red (where the helicity is positive). Snapshots of instantaneous tip clearance flow structure at four different times within a stator passing period are shown as $T/4$, $2T/4$, $3T/4$, and T .

Figure 4. Snapshots of Q criterion iso-surface colored by the normalized helicity

The tip leakage vortex is resolved in all cases with an almost identical trajectory. Meanwhile, a significant difference in the richness of the vortical structure in the tip region is shown between URANS and DES cases. The multiple induced vortices and the relative rotation between the induced vortices and the tip leakage vortex are resolved in both DES-Ave and DES-Wake cases.

The unsteadiness of tip clearance flow is reduced in URANS-Ave and DES-Ave cases because the steam turbine stage is working at a near-design point and the incoming external distortion is not considered. Comparison between URANS-Ave and URANS-Wake results indicates that the influence of stator wakes on the tip leakage vortex structure is minor. Meanwhile, in DES-Wake case, periodic motion of induced vortices in the tip region can be recognised in a

stator passing period due to the distortion of the stator wakes. Comparing with the structure of induced vortices resolved in DES-Ave case, migration of induced vortices near the blade trailing edge is presented in DES-Wake results.

The influence of stator wakes on time-averaged tip clearance flow structure is shown in Fig. 5-7 by the time-averaged Mach number contour at various span surfaces. The flow direction is from left to right in these contours, and the suction side of the blade is on the top of the figure.

Figure 5. Time-averaged Mach number contour at 90% span

Figure 6. Time-averaged Mach number contour at 96% span

Figure 7. Time-averaged Mach number contour at 98% span

The time-averaged flow field at 90% span is almost identical in all cases, which indicates that the influence of stator wake on the time-averaged flow field at 90% span is minor. However, a significant difference is shown between URANS and DES cases on the rear half of the suction side at 96% and 98% span, where the induced vortices structure is not resolved in URANS results. The migration of induced vortices near the trailing edge due to the stator wake effect generates a difference in averaged Mach number distribution between DES-Ave and DES-Wake results at 98% span.

As a conclusion, the influence of stator wake on the tip leakage vortex in this steam turbine model is small. Also, the induced vortices that are only resolved by DES display a periodic motion and migration due to the distortion of the stator wakes. A difference between URANS and DES results on time-averaged flow field is shown on the rear half of the suction side near the blade tip. Meanwhile, the influence of stator wake on the time-averaged flow field is minor, except for the induced vortices migration region that is resolved in DES-Wake case.

Blade loading

The time-averaged blade loading at 90%, 96% and 98% spans on the rotor blade in the four cases are shown in Fig. 8-10.

Figure 8. Time-averaged blade loading at 90% span

Figure 9. Time-averaged blade loading at 96% span

Figure 10. Time-averaged blade loading at 98% span

The influence of stator wakes and numerical approaches on time-averaged blade loading agree with the trends of the time-averaged flow field. The loading computed by the four cases are almost identical at the pressure side of all spans and the suction side of 90% span. Meanwhile, the influence of stator wakes on blade loading is minor in URANS cases at all spans.

From Fig. 9 and 10, consideration of the stator wake decreases the difference in the steady blade loading between DES and URANS approaches, especially at the 98% span. The primary source of loading difference between URANS-Ave and DES-Ave cases on the rear half of the suction side near the tip is the induced vortices [15]. Due to the periodic motion and migration of the induced vortices near blade trailing edge, the amplitude of loading difference is reduced with the impact of stator wake. However, the difference in blade loading between URANS-Wake and DES-Wake cases is still significant on the 96% span.

The pressure fluctuation on blade surface in the URANS-Ave and DES-Ave cases are minor (less than 1% of local time-averaged blade loading), for the steam turbine stage is working at a near-design point with no incoming external distortion and no blade motion. Meanwhile, the distortion by stator wake can generate an unsteady loading on the rotor blade with the same frequency as stator passing. The amplitude of unsteady loading in URANS-Wake and DES-Wake cases is calculated from the results in the last two stator-passing period after achieving the periodic flow solution. Distribution of the unsteady loading among the blade chord at 90%, 96%, and 98% spans are shown in Fig. 11-13.

Figure 11. Amplitude of unsteady blade loading at 90% span

Figure 12. Amplitude of unsteady blade loading at 96% span

Figure 13. Amplitude of unsteady blade loading at 98% span

High amplitude of unsteady pressure fluctuation is shown near the leading edge at all three spans due to the excitation of the stator wakes. Meanwhile, the distribution of unsteady blade loading shows a good agreement between URANS-Wake and DES-Wake cases except on the rear half of the suction side at 96% and 98% span where there is a significant increase in the amplitude of the unsteady pressure. This phenomenon is due to the unsteadiness of induced vortices resolved by DES which is much higher than that resolved by URANS, as shown in the flow field analysis in this paper and the prior research [6].

The stator passing frequency is generally much higher than the modal frequencies prone to flutter. Therefore, the influence of unsteady blade loading due to the impact of stator wake on rotor flutter characteristics can be insignificant if the tip leakage vortex structure is stable during the blade oscillation. However, an investigation of steam turbine flutter characterises by DES illustrates that the induced vortices are moving in the chordwise with the vibration of blade, which influences the wall work coefficient distribution on the suction side of blade near tip. Influence of the interaction between stator wakes and tip leakage flow on the steam turbine flutter characteristic is still required to be further analyzed.

CONCLUSION

The interaction between stator wake and rotor tip leakage flow in a 3D realistic-scale last stage steam turbine model is investigated by both URANS and DES approaches in this paper. The application of the DES method resolves the periodic motion of tip leakage flow structure due to the upstream wake effects.

The influence of numerical approaches and unsteady stators wakes on overall stage performance is minor. The energy level of turbulence kinetic energy in the tip clearance flow region in DES-Wake case is higher than that in DES-Ave case at every turbulence length scale, for the interaction with stator wakes significantly increase the turbulence intensity in the flow field.

Influence of stator wakes on the structure and trajectory of the tip leakage vortex is insignificant in this steam turbine model. Meanwhile, the induced vortices display a periodic

motion and migration near the trailing edge due to the distortion of the stator wake. Since the induced vortices are not resolved by URANS results, the influence of stator wake on tip clearance flow cannot be fully resolved by URANS analysis.

The time-averaged flow field and steady blade loading are almost identical at the pressure side of all spans and the suction side of 90% span in the four cases. Meanwhile, the influence of stator wakes on the averaged flow field is minor in URANS simulations. The distribution of unsteady blade loading shows a good agreement between URANS-Wake and DES-Wake cases except on the rear half of the suction side near the tip, for the unsteadiness of induced vortices resolved by DES is much higher than that resolved by URANS.

Consideration of the stator wake effects decreases the difference in time-averaged blade loading between DES and URANS cases, especially at the 98% span. However, the difference in steady blade loading between URANS-Wake and DES-Wake cases is still significant on the 96% span. Meanwhile, prior research illustrated that the relative motion of induced vortices resolved in DES cases could influence the aerodynamic work distribution on the blade during blade oscillation. Further investigation of the importance of multi-row effects on steam turbine flutter characteristics will be conducted in the future.

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